

The importance of Brain, Behaviour and Cognition research in changing times and landscapes: Challenges, opportunities and future prospects

Short title: Current challenges and prospects for BCB research

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Abstract:

Research in the field of brain, cognition and behaviour (BCB) is highly relevant for education, safety, healthcare, and policy making. For this white paper, a large group of researchers in the Netherlands united to highlight the paramount importance of fundamental BCB research for society and to chart the essential next steps for the BCB field, including concrete recommendations for governments, funders, universities/academic institutions, and individual scientists. This agenda includes the necessary actions to maintain and bolster the virtuous circle of fueling innovation through fundamental BCB research to address the current and future societal challenges. To this end, we outline highlights of BCB research: its societal impact on the fields of healthcare, education and safety, and its fundamental impact on scientific knowledge. We characterize fundamental science as a crucial driver of innovation and impact. We reflect on the important challenges that the field faces in the Netherlands and in Europe: reduced societal and political trust in science, misinformation about brain function, budget cuts, threats to experimental research with animals, and limits to internationalization. We stress that BCB science is inherently multidisciplinary and call for a research agenda and funding schemes that transcend traditional boundaries, foster interdisciplinary collaborations, internationalization, team science, and open science practices. The Dutch BCB research agenda is broadly relevant, and can inspire BCB research and interdisciplinary initiatives across Europe and globally. This agenda lays a path toward a resilient, responsive, and socially embedded BCB research ecosystem—one that is equipped to conquer scientific frontiers while fulfilling societal needs.

1. Introduction

1.1. Putting brain, cognition, and behavior research in perspective

The brain is one of the most fascinating organs in our body. With its approximately 86 billion neurons and 100 trillion synapses, the brain forms the foundation of all our perceptions, thoughts, and actions. Understanding how the brain works and influences behavior is not only an exciting and promising frontier of science, but also a powerful lever for societal innovation. For instance, major breakthroughs in artificial intelligence have been made possible through discoveries about how cellular networks in the brain are organized. Insights into the development of the adolescent brain have important implications for parental advice regarding for instance the use of social media (e.g., Liu et al., 2022). In addition, deeper knowledge of brain and behavioral deficits in brain-related disorders (like depression and anxiety) allows us to personalize treatment and prevention efforts, so that we are better able to help people when they need it and in the best possible way. These are just a few examples of the insights that Brain, Cognition, and Behaviour (BCB) research can offer - insights that are relevant for multiple domains, including education, safety, healthcare, and that are crucial for evidence-based and informed policy decisions.

1.2 Current threats to BCB research

The current political, societal and global developments have brought about serious threats for BCB research. First and foremost, we witness a substantial reduction in funding (particularly for fundamental research) due to shifting political landscapes (Rathenau report, 2025). In times of fast technological developments and global unprecedented challenges, this trend is not only difficult to understand, but also dangerously counterproductive. Interdisciplinary fundamental science is necessary to maintain a prepared and resilient society, and yet funding options for interdisciplinary BCB research are becoming scarcer. Younger academics experience this challenge the most, as they are faced with severely limited to non-existent career possibilities, leading to loss of talent, and 'brain drain'. Second, we also witness a general societal tendency to limit internationalization, including university-specific measures to reduce the influx of international students. This affects science globally, including the Netherlands that has a globally leading position in internationalization (Elsevier report, 2024). A third and concerning trend is the declining societal and political support for science: even though Dutch citizens have more trust in scientific organisations compared to most other institutions (such as newspapers or government; Rathenau, 2025), only a minority maintains a positive attitude towards science and technology in the Netherlands (Alaimo et al., 2025). In the era of widespread online misinformation, e.g., about the risk of vaccines, or the actual evidence for climate change. Facts about brain function can be prone to misinterpretation, such as the belief that we only use 10% of our brain (see [Wikipedia](#), or [Encyclopedia Britannica](#)). Indeed, it was found that there is a high prevalence of neuromyths among parents and teachers (Benneker et al., 2023; Torrijos-Muelas et al., 2021). Addressing these challenges requires a coordinated effort within and outside the BCB field.

1.3 The importance of BCB research

In response to these developments, a group of BCB researchers from the Netherlands wrote this white paper to call attention to the importance of BCB research. The initiative for this paper originated at a workshop organized by two BCB organisations (see section 2 for more details). As such, this paper is a concerted community effort of BCB scientists in the Netherlands to outline current challenges for the field and set out a shared agenda for the next decade on how we can keep contributing to the broader scientific and societal landscape.

Fundamental research, innovation, and societal challenges are core processes acting in dynamic and reciprocal interplay, as is visualized in the Research Impact Cycle (Figure 1). This schematic visualization integrates ideas from traditional linear innovation models with more recent proposals that posit the co-evolution of innovation with societal needs (Mazzucatto, 2017), as well as the Responsible Research Innovation model promoted by the Horizon 2020 program of the European Union (European Commission, 2013). Extrapolating on this model, below in section 2 we highlight successful examples of fundamental BCB research and its applications, in section 3 discuss current societal challenges, and in section 4 establish a research agenda with concrete recommendations and a future outlook for innovation in the field of BCB research. By setting a new standard for collaborative and interdisciplinary science we expect that this document will become an important resource for scientists, policy makers, funders and interested laypeople more generally. We also envision that by highlighting the interplay between fundamental research, society, and innovation in the Netherlands, this paper will provide important lessons that can be relevant for establishing the stability of independent and interdisciplinary BCB research in an international context.

Figure 1. The research impact cycle visualizes the dynamic interplay between societal challenges, fundamental research, and innovation.

1.4 The Dutch situation

The Netherlands ranks among the top 10 most productive countries in the world in the field of BCB research, with a growing publication share (Yeung et al., 2017; Simard et al., 2023). The Netherlands is also at the forefront of methodological and technological innovation in BCB research. Some examples are the recent initiative to build the world’s most powerful MRI scanner

(14 tesla, financed by the NWO roadmap grant, DYNAMIC project) and The Netherlands Brain Bank, collecting human brain tissue of patients with Alzheimer's disease since 1985, as well as brain tissues of people with other disorders and healthy participants. In several Dutch cities, long-term large-scale longitudinal behavioral, neuroimaging and biomarker studies continue to run (e.g., Van Bakel & Riksen-Walraven, 2002; Penninx et al., 2008; Kooijman et al., 2016; Crone et al., 2020; Meinders et al., 2020; Onland-Moret et al., 2020; Scholtens et al., 2015; Vacaru et al., 2022). These examples highlight the ambition, scope, quality, and diversity of BCB research in the Netherlands.

The Dutch research landscape is characterized by interconnected academic hubs and research institutes. Almost all Dutch universities host BCB research groups, often embedded in interdisciplinary faculties or institutes combining psychology, neuroscience, biology, artificial intelligence, mathematics, physics and data science. The Netherlands is home to many internationally renowned institutes (see [Table 1](#), Supplementary materials), strong national infrastructure (such as [Health-RI](#)), and many leading national and international collaborative initiatives. Prominent examples are the interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary innovation platform of the Netherlands Brain Initiative (Nationaal Plan Hoofdzaken) and the international educational program of [NeurotechEU](#). In sum, the Netherlands embodies a vibrant state-of-the-art ecosystem for BCB research. In this landscape, Dutch BCB research contributes to many topics in the field ([Figure 2](#)).

The Netherlands also has a strong reputation in fostering the bidirectional interplay between fundamental research and addressing societal challenges - a key aspect of the research impact cycle. In 2015, Dutch citizens had the opportunity to list questions they deemed important for scientists to answer. This led to 12,000 questions that were clustered into 140 overarching themes and organized into 25 thematic routes, each addressing broad societal and scientific challenges. This initiative came to be known as the Dutch National Research Agenda ([Nationale Wetenschapsagenda, NWA](#)): a citizens-driven collection of topics to be prioritized to address urgent societal challenges, drive innovation, and support scientific progress. The NWA funding programme is organized along thematic routes, whereby researchers and various societal stakeholders jointly identify key questions and work toward solutions to complex problems alongside all relevant societal stakeholders.

NeuroLabNL (<https://neurolab.nl>) is one of these thematic routes, which includes four 'pillars' - all focused on the role of the brain and central nervous system: (1) Health (through the promotion of healthy behavior, but also through the development of new techniques to help people with physical and psychological disorders live a full life), (2) Safety (social safety through diagnostics, risk assessment, prevention and intervention to strengthen resilience to reduce antisocial behavior), (3) Education (optimizing educational and social context to increase the ideal learning environment) and (4) Fundamental (understanding underlying brain processes to gain new insights in how the brain works). The research within these themes (see [Figure 2](#) for most used keyphrases) has led to valuable insights and practical applications, some of which we highlight in section 3.

Figure 2: Trends in BCB keyphrases. Non-exhaustive overview of most commonly used terms in BCB articles from the last 10 years of which at least one author is affiliated at a Dutch institute (based on our own SciVal analysis using text mining to extract keyphrases – see Appendix 2). Font size indicates relative frequency and colors indicate its trends over time.

With the support of NeuroLabNL and the Dutch BCB community more broadly, the Brain Cognition and Behavior – Netherlands (BCB-NL) platform was founded in 2020 to unite Dutch researchers in neuroscience, psychology, cognitive science, and related fields, fostering an interdisciplinary and collaborative approach to brain and behavior research. BCB-NL aims to advance both fundamental and applied research to increase impact, and advocates for greater visibility and support for this research domain, engaging with governmental funding agencies (NWO; ZonMW), universities, and research initiatives (e.g., NeuroLabNL; Young NeuroLabNL; the Netherlands Brain Initiative) to promote funding and policy alignment. Through organized knowledge exchange, lobbying efforts, networking events, and outreach, BCB-NL enhances the impact of brain and behavior research, enabling the different organizations in this field to connect and speak with one voice.

2. Why is fundamental research on the brain, cognition, and behavior important?

Fundamental research in the BCB field focuses on unraveling the workings of the brain and behavior in healthy individuals (and groups), as well as the mechanisms that lead to and maintain (psycho)pathology.

2.1 Curiosity-driven fundamental research drives knowledge development

Unlike applied research, which targets immediate and known problems, fundamental BCB research (also known as curiosity-driven research) is essential to understand how we think, feel, and interact with the world. Fundamental research topics in our field include amongst others language, cognition, consciousness, emotions, motivation, circadian rhythm, brain plasticity, and sensory perception. Generating and increasing our knowledge about these topics provides the cornerstone for applied research developments and implementations. As an example, fundamental neuroscientific research about how people make decisions and learn about the world has improved our understanding of impulsivity and aggression, but also of prosocial behavior in adolescents (e.g., Crone et al., 2021, 2022). This has in turn led to important insights in understanding inequality and poverty. Understanding the brain reward system in humans and animals has led to breakthroughs in the treatment of addiction, ADHD, Parkinson's disease, anxiety and depression (Volkow et al., 2016, Husain & Roiser 2018, Whitton et al., 2015, Luman et al., 2010, Cremers & Roelofs 2016). Research showing that grid cell activity (a particular type of hippocampal brain cell) is compromised in young adults at risk of Alzheimer's (Kunz et al., 2015) and in age-related navigational deficits (Stangl et al., 2018) was only possible after years long fundamental research in rats that had identified grid cells (Nobel Prize; O'Keefe, Moser & Moser, 2014).

Insights from BCB research are especially important in a rapidly changing world, with new emerging technologies, and a surge in mental health problems that pose unprecedented challenges for the healthcare system. This view is also strongly supported by the European Research Council (Munari et al., 2022; Nagar et al., 2024), which recently called for doubling investment in research and innovation, with a particular focus on the impact of curiosity-driven fundamental research. Basic scientific insights gained from BCB research are translated into concrete applications by governmental and medical institutes, applied universities, and a spectrum of not-for-profit and corporate organizations, which are optimally positioned to bridge theory and practice (see [Table 1](#)).

2.2 BCB research is highly interdisciplinary and helps develop methods and technologies

To gain insight in the interdisciplinary nature of BCB research, we conducted a bibliographic analysis of the different outputs for the BCB field according to scientific discipline (see [Figure 3](#)). BCB Research seeks to uncover the mechanisms that govern brain and cognitive (dys)function and behavior, and their interaction with other biological systems (such as the peripheral nervous system, the gut, etc.) and across multiple levels of analysis (genes, cells, circuits, multi-agent, varying contexts). This requires a variety of cutting-edge research methods, including

neuroimaging (from cellular to systems levels, with non-invasive and invasive methods), lab-based studies with humans and research animals, real-life and field studies (with mobile technology), and computational modeling. BCB researchers help to develop these tools, often in interdisciplinary collaborations with for example engineers or mathematicians.

Figure 3: Interdisciplinarity of BCB research. BCB outputs co-authored by researchers affiliated to Dutch institutions are published in a diverse range of journal subject area classifications (*SciVal analysis based on Elsevier classifications*). Note that publications are often mapped to multiple subject areas, so the total is >100%. The most general journals (such as Nature, Science, PlosONE, PNAS) are assigned only to Multidisciplinary.

2.3 Applications that were driven by fundamental BCB research

Insights from fundamental research have consistently led to translational and applied impact. In our rapidly changing world, it is often not efficient or effective to start from the problem and find a specific solution: this may take too long and come too late or at a high cost. Instead, existing fundamental knowledge affords solutions for unexpected problems (exemplified by Covid vaccinations building on a foundation of fundamental research). Below, we list a number of examples, where early findings in BCB research in diverse contexts, later proved useful to address societal challenges.

2.3.1 Brain health

Approximately 60% of the European population lives with a neurological or psychiatric condition (Source: [European Brain Council](#)). Alzheimer’s, Parkinson’s disease and major depressive disorder affect more than 4 million people in the Netherlands (Source: [Hersenstichting](#)). The Netherlands, just like other European countries, has a growing aging population, leading to rising incidences of neurodegenerative and neuroinflammatory diseases. Brain-related disorders cause major physical, mental, and social life impairments in affected people, and their family and friends. Associated yearly health care costs are approximately 31 billion euros ([RIVM](#), 2023), which amounts to one-third of the national health care budget. BCB research has been crucial to

improve our understanding of the mechanisms of common neurological and psychiatric disorders, which in turn allow improved preventative strategies and treatment outcomes. Cognitive neuroscience findings have also shaped public health policy by informing new policies around the legal drinking driving age, encouraging physical activity to improve brain health, and informing safe sports practices to reduce the risk of brain damage (e.g., Lammers et al., 2011; van den Eijnden et al., 2011).

2.3.2 Education and safety

Insights into brain mechanisms, learning, memory, attention and social interactions have informed educational developments. Recent applications are the decision by the Dutch government to ban smartphones from classrooms in secondary schools ([Kennisnet, 2024](#)), and the development of an app that monitors social dynamics in the classroom to promote a safe social environment in schools ([stoeltjesdans](#), used by over 27.000 teachers in the Netherlands and Flanders). Applications like these have been driven by BCB research on attention, distraction, resilience and adolescent brain development (reviewed in Sneep, 2025). As another example, curiosity-driven BCB research on resilience, stress and biofeedback (Klaassen et al., 2025) has also led to the development of a new virtual reality application using bio-feedback to increase stress resilience in police officers. This training is now being implemented in police academies, and the research insights are further being utilized to extend this intervention to reduce aggression among police officers and at-risk youth (see [link](#)). Insights into drivers of behavioral change turn out to be of paramount importance for societal problems such as climate change and healthy lifestyles. BCB research on impulsivity, resilience, personality disorders, and posttraumatic stress disorder have all been essential for developing evidence-based safety policies.

2.3.3 Technological developments

New technologies in neuroscience have led to the identification of over 5000 brain cell types (BICCN, 2023). We can now measure brain activity with unprecedented resolution using ultra-dense neurophysiology, ultrahigh-field MRI, and optically pumped magnetometers. In animals, optical, electronic, and genetic tools enable long-term recording and targeted manipulation of brain circuits to reveal causal mechanisms. In humans, non-invasive neuromodulation (e.g., transcranial magnetic stimulation, transcranial direct current stimulation, focused ultrasound stimulation, neurofeedback) enables modulation of brain activity for both research and therapeutic purposes. Mobile technologies and wearable devices now support real-world brain and behavior monitoring, enabling deeper insights into how neural processes unfold in daily life. Wearable neurotech devices enables communication and control (e.g., Verbaarschot et al. 2021), rehabilitation (e.g., Musso et al. 2022), diagnostics (e.g., Guyonnet-Hencke et al. 2025), unobtrusive monitoring of stress and mental health in daily life (Tutunji et al., 2023), as well as monitoring of patients' cognitive, social and motor symptoms in daily life (Jagessar et al., 2021), improving personalized care. Novel technologies have helped identify specific brain circuits involved in Parkinson's disease, allowing targeted treatment using (adaptive) deep brain stimulation (e.g., Dold et al. 2025). Similarly, neuropixel electrode arrays and optogenetics help clarify how dopamine circuits malfunction in Parkinson's disease, guiding the development of

more precise therapies (e.g., Gradinaru et al., 2009). These trends in technological developments highlight the innovative potential of BCB research and development.

2.3.4 Animal research contributes to advancing brain research

About 10% of all animal studies that are conducted in the EU concern nervous system research. The number of animals used yearly for nervous system research equals about 0.03% of the number of pigs, cows, sheep and goats in Europe's livestock population (Sources: [European Commission](#) in 2022; [EU eurostat](#) in 2023). Animal research in Europe is carried out only when there is no suitable non-animal alternative, as resolved in EU law ([Directive 2010/63](#)), and when adhering to the guidelines to ensure animals' welfare (formulated in the same law, and supported by the Federation of European Neurosciences' [CARE committee](#)). For some of the fundamental, applied, and clinical questions in BCB research, alternatives are often unavailable due to the complexity of the brain and the importance of interactions with the environment (Martinez-Sanchez et al., 2016; Homberg et al., 2021). The field has generated many insights and innovations based on animal experiments. For example, cochlear implants can aid hearing in the deaf and have been developed based on experiments with chickens, rabbits, cats, pigs, and non-human primates (Reiss et al., 2022), and surgical interventions using deep brain stimulation in people with Parkinson's disease were developed through experiments in non-human primates (Wichmann et al., 2018).

Yet, growing ethical concerns and attention to alternative research methods have led to increased scrutiny of its necessity (e.g., [FENS position paper, 2018](#); Homberg et al., 2021). Misaligned with the essential role of animal models in research, policymakers are working toward the adoption of non-animal approaches. As such, we emphasize that animal experimentation, where no suitable alternatives are available, remains of utmost importance in addressing societal challenges and in driving innovations in essential domains that cannot be achieved via other approaches.

2.4 Future topics and areas of BCB research

The BCB community (through our [survey included in the supplementary online materials](#)) has identified research topics that closely reflect looming societal challenges, and that should be addressed in the coming 10 years. In line with several priorities outlined in the National Dutch Research Agenda (NWA), this list of research topics could guide future coordinated efforts of the BCB field:

1. Mental health across the lifespan
2. Early detection and treatment of neurodegenerative disorders
3. Brain health and the impact of societal and environmental stressors
4. Individual differences and personalized medicine
5. The effects of digital environments on cognition and well-being

These topics reflect the felt need to address societal issues related to health and disease. At the same time, BCB research on these topics has increasingly come under pressure due to current

societal and scientific challenges. Addressing these challenges seems especially timely given that the freedom and independence of academic research have come increasingly under threat.

3. What are the current challenges for BCB research?

3.1 Lack of sufficient funding for fundamental and interdisciplinary research

One pressing concern is the diminishing support for independent fundamental research, while the personnel costs and material costs have only increased. Political and institutional shifts have placed increasing emphasis on (short-term) thematic and applied research, narrowing the space for curiosity-driven inquiry. At the same time, curiosity-driven ‘blue sky research’ at the European level (i.e., ERC grants) lead to more patent applications and interventions compared to grants that have a more applied focus (ERC, 2025; Newsbyte, 2019). Structural funding that supports interdisciplinary and long-term collaborations is suboptimal in the Netherlands. So-called ‘first-stream funds’ (i.e., funds from the government directly to universities to carry out fundamental research) have progressively decreased, to the point that many researchers lack access to basic infrastructure or the means to conduct experiments, as there is limited to non-existent internal funding to appoint PhD students or postdocs. ‘Second-stream’ funds (from national funding agencies such as NWO), have become hyper-competitive, and these agencies also face government-imposed budget cuts. At a national level, there is an increased tendency for programmatic and directly applied research (through funding consortia), while programs for fundamental and independent research are in jeopardy. With extremely low success rates for grants, enormous resources are wasted on unfunded applications. Grant application comes at considerable burden for researchers and universities (as scientists write grants in their free time, on top of their regular tasks, exacerbating work pressure), as well as for funding agencies (where the review process is very costly and time-consuming). With funding scarcity and low award rates, the cost of the application process often substantially outweighs the highly uncertain gain (Dresler et al., 2023). This challenge affects all researchers, yet with especially dramatic consequences for early-career researchers (see also: 3.2).

A related challenge pertains to funding interdisciplinary research projects that cut across the boundaries of different scientific disciplines. Specifically, there is a lack of funding instruments for interdisciplinary collaborations between researchers within institutions. Despite their demonstrably greater likelihood to result in scientific breakthroughs and innovations, interdisciplinary proposals have a lower chance of getting funded (see e.g., Bourguignon, 2019). Existing panels and domains within funding agencies often do not fit well with the interdisciplinary approach that is key to BCB research.

3.2 Need for sustainable career-development

Academic career tracks have progressively become less attractive because of extremely high competition, lack of job security, and very high workload with high rates of work-related mental health complaints and stress (Roach & Sauerman, 2017). A major factor in the workload stems from teaching and administrative tasks beyond the contractually assigned time. The high teaching load is currently exacerbated by budget cuts on higher education, which have already

jeopardized ongoing projects. The combination of systemically high work pressure with budget cuts is bound to cripple the innovation potential for the coming years, and will reduce competitiveness, in turn resulting in a loss of external funding.

In times of additional budget cuts in higher-education in the Netherlands, career prospects for BCB postdoctoral researchers and PhD students have become concerningly narrow, especially for first-generation academics (KNAW, 2025) and for researchers who balance family responsibilities and/or have limited mobility options. This results in the inability of universities to attract or retain talent (e.g., by offering a permanent position), including the talent they trained at considerable cost and time. The situation for early career tenured researchers (assistant professors) is not encouraging either: they usually start their independent research track in combination with a heavy teaching load and no start-up funds for research assistance, materials, or PhD students (as is common practice in other countries). There is also no harmonized tenure-track system or policy in the Netherlands, with clear promotion rules and guidelines to move from assistant, to associate or full professor. Decreasing funds and an increased national trend towards funding large consortia (e.g., Gravitation grants, NWA) further limit the possibilities for talent development and early-career researchers. Very few funding schemes are accessible for PhD students or postdocs, and these have become competitive to the point that young scientists have been advocating for a switch from current evaluation procedures to a lottery format (see: The Young Academy, 2024).

The BCB field in particular is facing serious struggles, as brain research relies on cutting-edge yet expensive techniques and materials and advanced technical knowledge built over years of training.

3.3 Threats to internationalization

Political actions to limit internationalization—capping the influx of international students and staff—further threaten the diversity, excellence, and international competitiveness of Dutch research institutions. In the past 10 years, researchers based in the Netherlands have performed very well in securing European funds (ERIS, ERC Research Information System analysis: the Netherlands ranked third in receiving ERC funding at 12.8%, directly following Germany and France). This ability to rival much larger countries is reflected in the high quality of BCB research in the Netherlands, amplified by its ability to attract and retain world-class international talent. International bachelor, master and research master programs allow Dutch universities to attract talented international students, who often proceed with a career in academia. These programs in turn also attract talented international faculty to train and mentor the next generation of researchers. However, with the current developments (e.g., cutting the international bachelor program in psychology) and political climate, this excellence, and hence the international competitiveness of Dutch BCB research, is in jeopardy.

3.4 Declining support for science

We increasingly live in an era of misinformation and ‘alternative facts’. In the Netherlands, fewer people have a positive attitude towards science than in many other European countries (Alaimo

et al., 2025), a worrying trend that undermines the role of science in informing policy and public discourse. Despite the fact that across-the-board trust in science is still higher than trust in many other institutions (Rathenau Instituut, 2025), high-profile initiatives such as the Human Brain Project (Markram, 2012) have faced disillusionment about the tangible impact of brain research. At the same time, for the majority of people who *do* have a trust in science, it is not always easy to know where and how to find reliable information, e.g., about brain function and health. BCB research faces an important task to debunk unsubstantiated claims (e.g., playing Mozart makes babies smarter) and pseudoscientific facts about the brain (e.g., the left hemisphere is for analytical thinking and the right for intuitive processing, or that brain training games will make you smarter). There are also some beliefs for which we currently still lack sufficient evidence, such as the claim that smartphones in general have a negative impact on the brain health of youth. These neuromyths appear widespread among the general population, especially in parents and teachers (Benneker et al., 2023; Torrijos-Muelas et al., 2021). Together, these issues are threats that undermine the importance of long-term, foundational investigation of BCB topics.

3.5 Societal challenges

Our society faces many complex problems—including mental health crises, neurodegenerative diseases, poverty, challenges in education, the climate and energy crisis, international conflicts, migration, safety, and the risks of AI. These societal problems carry immense financial costs. For example, the estimated financial burden of mental health problems is around a yearly 4% of the GDP in European countries - amounting to an expense of more than 27 billion euros on health issues (European Commission, 2024). These costs put an enormous strain on the healthcare system and negatively impact people’s mental and physical wellbeing. These problems also present a challenge to the vitality and sustainability of our society in the future. Reduced funding opportunities, bureaucratic hurdles, and institutional constraints currently limit researchers’ capacity to contribute solutions.

These challenges and concerns are also shared by the Dutch BCB community - as evidenced in a survey that we conducted among 55 BCB researchers in the Netherlands to get their perspective on the most pressing issues (see [supplementary material online](#)). These challenges pose a serious threat not just to the scientific enterprise but to the long-term societal benefits that BCB research provides. Addressing them requires coordinated action, structural investment, and a renewed commitment to the value of fundamental science.

4. What are the proposed solutions for fostering innovation with BCB research?

We have argued that fundamental BCB research is a key propellant in pushing innovation towards a resilient and adaptable society. As we look to the future, it is vital to chart a research agenda that balances scientific excellence, societal relevance, and sustainable infrastructure, which in turn drives innovation (i.e., as reflected in the research cycle, [Figure 1](#)). The key identified catalysts for effective innovation are systemic financial support, fundamental curiosity-driven research, interdisciplinarity, internationalization, and sustainable career paths for early career scientists. Below we outline concrete recommendations for governments, funders, grant agencies, policy-makers, and researchers to meet these needs.

4.1 For governments, policy-makers and funding agencies

4.1.1 Structural and increased support for scientific innovation is a top priority to address societal challenges, but the Netherlands has one of the lowest investment rates in research and development in Europe: less than 2.5% of its GDP, which is below European guidelines (e.g., [TNO report](#)) and much lower than countries like Belgium and Germany. Without increased structural investments in fundamental research, we will lose our position at the forefront and pioneering frontiers of scientific excellence, competitiveness and innovation. A similar pledge has been made at the EU level ([European Brain Council, 2023](#)).

Recommendations:

- **Increase structural funding** for research and development to maintain and bolster the high-quality BCB research infrastructure in the Netherlands. The Dutch royal academy of sciences (KNAW) recommends a minimum of 3% of the GDP, matching European guidelines. Ideally, investment policy should follow the virtuous example of highly competitive EU countries, that go **above 3.5%**).
- **Specifically increase first-stream funding to universities** to guarantee minimum necessary resources. This is essential to maintain international competitiveness, functioning infrastructure, state-of-the-art facilities, and research feasibility in terms of material costs and researchers' time (research hours, which have progressively decreased under the pressure of heavier teaching tasks as a consequence of budget cuts).

4.1.2 Curiosity-driven research is essential to bolster innovation when facing unprecedented societal challenges. As clearly stated by the European Research Council (2024): *"In view of increasing global competition, time is running out for Europe to maintain its competitive edge in global science and technology. To keep pace, an essential step is to modernise the long-term EU budget and to double the spending for research and innovation ([press release 24 January 2024](#))"*. Now more than ever, this is applicable to the Netherlands, where research funds - particularly for fundamental curiosity-driven research - are progressively being reduced, while competition has spiked. Concretely, this plea entails protecting, and where possible expanding Talent Schemes, such as the NWO Veni-Vidi-Vici track (where in the last 7 years, award rates have

dropped to 13%; Source: [Annual NWO yearly report 2024](#)) and reintroducing early career Talent Schemes (for PhD projects).

Recommendations:

- **Increase funding for curiosity-driven research** (alongside thematic research).
- **Renew assessment systems for competitive funding schemes** in order to safeguard quality while increasing efficiency and reducing burden.
- **Provide support for early career researchers** in terms of start-up funds (meeting international standards), to avoid losing talent to other sectors and countries.
- **Reintroduce early-career talent schemes** (e.g. funding for individual phd projects, which allow exploring truly innovative research ideas).
- **Foster collaborations of academia with industry and/or societal and non-profit organisations in the Netherlands** by offering joint PhD scholarships and training in transferable skills (as in the successful international example of the Marie Curie Doctoral Networks calls by the EU Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe programs).

4.1.3 Interdisciplinarity involving multiple stakeholders and diverse perspectives has become the norm rather than the exception in BCB research. Yet, securing funding for interdisciplinary research remains a challenge. Formal recognition for **team science** is also lagging behind daily practice. Team science refers to the collaborative effort of individual scientists, each contributing unique skills necessary for successful fulfillment of project goals (Ghamgosar et al. 2023). While this is common practice in BCB research, the main sources of funding are personal grants, with recognition assigned to the principal investigator (PI), rather than to the team that contributed to the development of the research program.

Recommendations:

- **Calibrate funding schemes and awards to support and stimulate interdisciplinarity and team-science.** Expand funding schemes supporting inter- but also intra-institutional interdisciplinary team science. Award seed funds to support collaborations between PIs (including early and mid-career PIs as well. Seed fund allows exploring more innovative and risky ideas, with high-return on investment).
- **Reform evaluation and review processes** so that interdisciplinary proposals are fairly evaluated, e.g., by making sure that each proposal is reviewed by experts from different scientific disciplines by including interdisciplinarity as a key criterion for evaluation.
- **Acknowledge teamwork** in existing schemes (e.g., in Talent schemes, allow and encourage recognition of team members in the development of research proposals and projects), thereby enhancing the visibility and recognition of early-career researchers.

4.1.4 Internationalization is the cornerstone of a healthy scientific and educational ecosystem in our (academic) society. The Netherlands has the highest percentage of international collaborations in the world, with 63% of articles with Dutch authors having international co-authors (against the 20% world average and 43% European average; Elsevier report, 2024). The

international character of our universities needs to be safeguarded and boosted, which includes protecting and promoting our international bachelor programs. A welcoming attitude to and support for international researchers is needed to ensure we can keep attracting the most talented international students and staff.

Recommendations:

- **Safeguard English-taught bachelor and master programs** and internationalization policies within universities.
- **Keep on attracting international talent**, through the continued support of institutions aimed at bringing together international interdisciplinary groups of scholars. Successful showcases are the Netherlands Institute for Advanced Studies (NIAS) and the Lorentz Center, as well as academic centers of excellence (e.g., the Netherlands Institute for Neuroscience (NIN) - which is an institute of the Dutch Royal Academy of Sciences).
- **Provide and promote international mobility schemes**, such as the very successful European example of the Marie Curie Fellowship, part of Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe funding programs.

4.2 For universities and research institutions

4.2.1 Institutional support for interdisciplinary research is critical. Universities can play an important role in supporting (emerging) interdisciplinary fields by establishing assistant professor positions and PhD programs that straddle departments and faculties, and by creating and supporting research institutes focused on grand challenges requiring interdisciplinary approaches (e.g., brain-body interactions, AI in society, or mental health). They can also support novel interdisciplinary initiatives through specific internal funding schemes. The Netherlands already hosts several strong interdisciplinary research institutes and platforms in the field of BCB (see [Table 1](#)), that demonstrate the ability to integrate diverse fields to address complex scientific questions. This also entails supporting internationalization within universities, by enabling an open, inclusive, and diverse working environment, and deploying policies to attract and retain international talented researchers. Recent and looming budget cuts have brought these aspects under serious threat, putting international competitiveness at risk.

Recommendations:

- **Remove logistic and bureaucratic barriers** for inter-institutional and interdisciplinary collaboration by facilitating centralized infrastructures (e.g., Surf). Mitigate practical obstacles that hinder interdisciplinarity (separation between faculties, lack of resources).

- **Prioritize funding for interdisciplinary institutes and initiatives** (e.g., thematic hubs, existing and new interdisciplinary/interfaculty institutes).
- **Award stimulation funds** for inter-faculty inter-disciplinary collaborations.
- **Revise hiring, promotion, and research evaluation frameworks** to recognize interdisciplinary output, including collaborative papers, joint grants, and societal impact beyond disciplinary norms.
- **Develop and offer interdisciplinary education** (Bachelor and Master levels).
- **Facilitate national mobility** and transition of researchers across universities and institutionalize interdisciplinary career paths (e.g., joint appointments).
- **Safeguard English-taught bachelor programs** and internationalization policies within universities.
- **Retain and protect local inclusion and diversity policies**, which under pressure of the budget cuts are at risk of being disincentivized.

4.2.2 Sustainable career paths for early-career researchers and a transparent system for tenure-track and promotion are required to retain talented young people in academia. In line with the [Recognition and Rewards program](#), universities and research institutions should focus on diversifying career paths by recognizing the need for letting academics excel in either research, teaching or impact.

Recommendations:

- Promote conditions supporting a **realistic workload**, with balanced distribution of tasks, in line with the national [Recognition & Rewards movement](#).
- Support **temporary workload relief** when necessary and possible (e.g., with temporary teaching load reductions to apply for grants and by providing technical and administrative support).
- Allow **horizontal career development** (also including impact as a core task).
- Encourage and enact **adequate recognition** of early career contributions (in grant applications, research projects, committee work, management tasks, PhD-supervision etc.) and adjust academic reward structures to give recognition for interdisciplinary research and non-traditional research outputs.

4.3 For researchers

4.3.1 Science communication, public outreach, and citizen science: In an era of misinformation and high prevalence of neuromyths especially among teachers and parents (Benneker et al., 2023; Torrijos-Muelas et al., 2021), outreach is not a luxury—it is a necessity. A more centralized communication infrastructure, potentially coordinated by BCB-NL, could help amplify our collective voice and improve dialogue with policymakers and the public. We must also extend the reach of science communication beyond traditional audiences. Initiatives like citizen science, public festivals, podcasts, and educational programs (e.g., the Hoe?Zo! Show) have shown promise to engage the general public by contributing to science as well. These efforts need to be broadened to a truly diverse audience (e.g., with a migration background) with attention to inclusivity and equal opportunity. This means going beyond easy to reach groups. By tailoring

content to resonate with diverse communities and recognizing outreach efforts as core academic activities, we can cultivate a more inclusive and science-literate society at large. Additionally, we need to reconceptualize societal impact by considering the essential contribution of science communication at all stages of the research process. Drawing inspiration from the Research Impact Cycle (Figure 1), communicating science can and should happen during the development of research questions, during implementation, as well as after research findings are available. Communicating science is not only about the specific findings or about identifying which questions are relevant: a key aspect is spreading the knowledge that is already there, highlighting how science has guided innovation and positively influenced citizens living standards, next to quantifiable technological or business-related innovation (Alaimo et al., 2025).

Recommendations:

- **Scientific communication and public engagement training** should be structurally offered in academic training trajectories, starting at the PhD level.
- **Public engagement and science communication** at all stages of research should be recognized as a core academic task.

4.3.2 Team science, open science, and interdisciplinary collaborations are essential to safeguard the rigor and quality of BCB research. While coordinated action and support from funding agencies and research institutions is key, individual scientists can and should do their part in promoting recognition of team science, adopting and expanding open science practices, and actively pursuing interdisciplinary integration.

Recommendations:

- **Acknowledge and promote team science:** Credit structures should be reformed to recognize the diverse roles in collaborative projects, from data collection to conceptual leadership. Researchers can contribute by explicitly acknowledging team contributions in publications (e.g., through credit statements) and by advocating for inclusive authorship practices in their departments and fields. Adequate acknowledgements should also be included in grant applications (funding schemes permitting), moving away from an unrealistic 1-person and PI-centered enterprise that does not reflect the collaborative nature of most BCB research.
- **Expand and stimulate open science adoption:** Transparency should be the default. Researchers should pre-register studies, where possible share data, and share code openly to allow for reproducibility, and use open-access platforms (e.g., Open Science Framework, <https://osf.io>). Senior researchers have a particular responsibility to model and incentivize these practices within their research groups or labs and review work through the lens of reproducibility.
- **Shape institutional cultures:** Active participation in curriculum development, PhD committees, and interdisciplinary institutes can help align institutional policies with the values of team science, open science and interdisciplinarity.

- **Engage broader communities:** Research programs should include perspectives from patients, advocacy groups, and the general public. Bottom-up initiatives can enrich scientific inquiry and ensure that research addresses societal as well as academic needs.

4.3.3 Strengthening our societal positioning through dialogue and advocacy

To ensure that fundamental BCB research continues to thrive and serve society, we must strengthen our collective voice in the public and political arena. Despite its relevance to urgent societal challenges, BCB research is sometimes fragmented in its representation and underrepresented in national science and innovation policy (e.g., different initiatives exist with different aims and agendas such as the Netherlands Brain Initiative (Nationaal Plan Hoofdzaken), NeuroLabNL, BCB-NL, the Dutch Brain Foundation (Hersenstichting) etc.). A more concerted and proactive effort is needed. An organized effort could help positioning the BCB field more clearly in strategic policy dialogues with e.g., the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science (OCW), the Ministry of Health, Welfare, and Sport (VWS), the ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy (EZK), the Ministry of Social Affairs and Employment (SZW) and the ministry of defense (MinDef). At the same time, BCB researchers must improve their ability to listen to societal stakeholders and involve them meaningfully in shaping research agendas. Patient organizations, educators, youth workers, and mental health professionals hold valuable and necessary experiential and practical knowledge.

Recommendations:

- **Develop a structured and visible BCB advocacy strategy** at the national level (e.g., through establishing a Dutch Brain Council), aimed at influencing funding priorities, science agendas and political awareness.
- **Build durable partnerships with societal stakeholders** (e.g., patient organizations, educators, youth workers) and facilitate their participation in projects and grant applications.
- **Train researchers in stakeholder engagement** and science-policy communication as part of professional development.

5. Concluding remarks

As BCB researchers working in the Netherlands, we feel privileged to have the opportunity to contribute to world-class research, in an international context, with state-of-the-art facilities and in relative freedom to pursue our own research ideas. Hence, there is even more urgency to highlight that this position is currently in jeopardy, due to societal and scientific threats. Some of the issues we address in this white paper also apply to academic research more broadly: lack of funding, limited career possibilities for early-stage researchers, threats to internationalization and to interdisciplinary work. As such we see this paper as an opportunity to call attention to threats to the BCB field in particular and the academic field more broadly.

To meet these societal and scientific challenges of our time, the Netherlands must sustain and grow its world-class Brain, Cognition, and Behavior (BCB) research ecosystem. The research impact cycle (Figure 1) highlights the dynamic relation between fundamental science, societal needs, and innovation and offers a framework for facing these challenges. By investing strategically in curiosity-driven research, interdisciplinary collaboration, and open, inclusive science, we can discover new fundamental insights in brain functioning that improve health, education, safety, and well-being. The Dutch BCB community is well-organized, connected, and has a strong position in cutting-edge, upcoming research areas. With the necessary ingredients already in place, and the urgency of societal challenges, it is important that national and European governments will increase long-term investments in BCB research to maintain and strengthen our forefront position. Progressive and coordinated action from funders, policymakers, institutions, and researchers will ensure that BCB research remains the cornerstone of a resilient society, ready to meet the challenges ahead.

6. List of abbreviations

ADHD: Attention-Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder
BCB-NL: platform Brain, Cognition and Behavior – Netherlands
BCB: Brain, Cognition, and Behavior
EZK: The Dutch ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy
GDP: Gross Domestic Product
KNAW: The Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences
MinDef: The Dutch ministry of defense
MRI: Magnetic Resonance Imaging
NWA: Dutch National Research Agenda (*“Nationale Wetenschaps Agenda”*)
NWO: Dutch Research Council (*“Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek”*)
OCW: The Dutch Ministry of Education, Culture and Science
PI: Principal Investigator
PNAS: Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences
RIVM: The Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (*“Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu”*)
SciVal: brand name for research analytics tool
SZW: The Dutch Ministry of Social Affairs and Employment
TNO: Dutch Organisation for Applied Scientific Research
VWS: The Dutch Ministry of Health, Welfare, and Sport
ZonMW: not an abbreviation, but a collaboration between *ZorgOnderzoekNederland (Zon)* and *Medische Wetenschappen (MW)*.

7. Data sharing statement

We compiled overviews of information for this manuscript, which are included as supplementary materials (list of institutions, outcomes of a survey, and key phrases for bibliographic analysis). No further data was generated in this opinion paper.

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Supplementary Material Online

Table 1. Non-exhaustive overview of different academic and research institutions and organizations in the Netherlands involved in BCB research, from Bibliometric analysis (see Appendix 2).

Institution	Sector
Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences	Applied University
Avans University of Applied Sciences	Applied University
Fontys University of Applied Sciences	Applied University
HAN University of Applied Sciences	Applied University
Hanze University of Applied Sciences	Applied University
HKU University of the Arts Utrecht	Applied University
Hogeschool Zuyd	Applied University
InHolland University of Applied Sciences	Applied University
NHL Stenden University of Applied Sciences	Applied University
NHTV Breda University of Applied Sciences	Applied University
Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences	Applied University
Saxion University of Applied Sciences	Applied University
The Hague University of Applied Sciences	Applied University
University of Applied Sciences Leiden	Applied University
Utrecht University of Applied Sciences	Applied University
Van Hall Larenstein University of Applied Sciences	Applied University
Windesheim University of Applied Sciences	Applied University
Delft University of Technology	University
Eindhoven University of Technology	University
Erasmus University Rotterdam	University
Leiden University	University

Maastricht University	University
Nyenrode Business University	University
Open Universiteit	University
Radboud University Nijmegen	University
Tilburg University	University
University of Amsterdam	University
University of Groningen	University
University of Twente	University
Utrecht University	University
Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	University
Wageningen University & Research	University
Centrum voor Wiskunde en Informatica	Government
Dutch Health and Youth Care Inspectorate	Government
European Space Research and Technology Center (ESTEC)	Government
Max Planck Institute for Psycholinguistics	Government
Municipal Health Service of Amsterdam	Government
National Institute of Public Health and the Environment	Government
Netherlands Cancer Institute	Government
Netherlands Institute for Developmental Biology	Government
Netherlands Institute for Neuroscience	Government
Netherlands Institute for Radio Astronomy	Government
Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research	Government
Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences	Government
Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research - NIOZ	Government
Statistics Netherlands	Government
SURFsara	Government

World Health Organization	Government
Biomedical Primate Research Centre	Research Center
Center for Human Drug Research	Research Center
Donders Institute	Research Center
Holst Centre	Research Center
Lorentz Center	Research Center
Naturalis Biodiversity Center	Research Center
Netherlands eScience Center	Research Center
Netherlands Forensic Institute	Research Center
Netherlands Genomics Initiative	Research Center
Netherlands Institute for Advanced Studies	Research Center
Netherlands Institute for Health Services Research	Research Center
Netherlands Institute for Neuroscience	Research Center
Research School for Behavioural and Cognitive Neurosciences	Research Center
Roessingh Research and Development	Research Center
Royal Netherlands Aerospace Centre	Research Center
The Spinoza Centre for Neuroimaging	Research Center
TI Food and Nutrition	Research Center
Trimbos Institute	Research Center
Amphia Hospital	Medical
Amsterdam UMC	Medical
Antoni van Leeuwenhoek Hospital	Medical
Canisius Wilhelmina Hospital	Medical
Catharina Hospital	Medical
Deventer Ziekenhuis	Medical
ETZ Elisabeth	Medical

Gelderland Valley Hospital	Medical
Haaglanden Medisch Centrum	Medical
Haga Ziekenhuis	Medical
IJsselland Ziekenhuis	Medical
Isala Clinics	Medical
Jeroen Bosch Ziekenhuis	Medical
Kempenhaghe Epilepsy Centre	Medical
Maastad Hospital	Medical
Martini Ziekenhuis	Medical
Maxima Medical Centre	Medical
Meander Medical Center	Medical
Medical Centre Leeuwarden	Medical
Medisch Spectrum Twente	Medical
North West Hospital Group	Medical
Onze Lieve Vrouwe Gasthuis	Medical
Princess Máxima Center for Pediatric Oncology	Medical
Reinier de Graaf Groep	Medical
Rijndam Rehabilitation Center	Medical
Rijnstate Hospital	Medical
Slotervaart Hospital	Medical
Spaarne Gasthuis	Medical
St. Antonius Ziekenhuis	Medical
St. Martin Clinic	Medical
VieCuri Medisch Centrum	Medical
Ziekenhuisgroep Twente	Medical
Zuyderland	Medical

Epilepsy Institutes of the Netherlands Foundation	Specialized medical care
Interuniversity Cardiology Institute of the Netherlands	Specialized medical care
Parnassia Bavo Groep	Specialized medical care
Royal Dutch Kentalis	Specialized medical care
Sanquin Blood Supply Foundation	Not-for-profit organization
TNO	Not-for-profit organization
Adelante	Corporate organization
Brain Innovation B.V.	Corporate organization
PI Research Ltd	Corporate organization
ProQR Therapeutics	Corporate organization
Danone Nutricia Research	Corporate organization
GE HealthCare	Corporate organization
Johnson & Johnson	Corporate organization
Koninklijke Philips N.V.	Corporate organization
NXP Semiconductors	Corporate organization
Qualcomm Incorporated	Corporate organization
Siemens	Corporate organization
Thales	Corporate organization
Unilever	Corporate organization

Appendix 1. Survey Conducted at BCB workshop to identify current challenges and research agenda

While having brought about substantial scientific and societal innovation, the BCB field is facing important challenges. To summarize these key challenges, we have asked all workshop participants attending the “Dutch Brain Behaviour and Cognition Day” to fill in a short online survey. We collected responses from 55 participants, all BCB researchers in the Netherlands. Of these 24 indicated to work on fundamental neuroscience, 16 on the topic of health, 8 on education and 5 on safety. 16 participants were PhD students, 8 were postdocs and 31 were assistant professors or higher career researchers. We conducted a short-thematic analysis of open-ended responses using Qualitative Research Analysis GPT, which yielded 5 general themes, listed below:

1: Insufficient and Unstable Funding for Fundamental and Curiosity-Driven Research: A main concern was the lack of sustained funding for fundamental, curiosity-driven research, viewed as essential to innovation but increasingly sidelined by applied priorities and budget cuts. *Example Quote: “Budget cuts, which could limit research creativity and trying innovative hypotheses, thoughts and ideas”*

2: Fragmentation and Lack of Interdisciplinary Collaboration: Participants emphasized difficulties in fostering interdisciplinary cooperation and connecting across fields, noting the need for shared language, integration of methods, and broader scientific alliances. *Example quote: “Integrating methods and knowledge from different fields to foster collaboration and interdisciplinary research.”*

3: Weak Societal Engagement and Translation of Research: Respondents identified a gap between science and society, highlighting the challenge of making research relevant, inclusive, and accessible to the public and societal partners. *Example Quote: “Translate our research to society. Include societal partners in research, disseminate our findings”*

4: Political and Institutional Constraints: Concerns were raised about the influence of political agendas and unstable institutional policies that steer scientific direction, often at odds with researcher autonomy and scientific merit. *Example Quote: “The changing political climate and the influence of politicians that decide what is good/important science and what should not be studied.”*

5: Barriers to Career Development and Academic Sustainability: Particularly from early-career researchers, there were reports of job insecurity, high competition for grants, and structural instability limiting long-term career growth and continuity in research. *Example Quote: “From a*

point of view of a postdoc, a major challenge is navigating practical barriers like limited long-term funding [...] and extremely high competition for grants and permanent positions.”

At our workshop, we also asked all BCB researchers what they considered the most important topics for BCB research in the next 10 years to come. By conducting a thematic analysis of the 55 open-ended responses, the following themes for a research agenda were identified:

1. **Mental Health Across the Lifespan:** A central concern was improving mental health, particularly among youth and in the context of adversity, including societal stressors, psychiatric disorders, and rising digital technology use. *Example quote: “How do we improve mental health in young people?”*
2. **Early detection, understanding, and treatment of neurodegenerative and psychiatric disorders, as well as brain health promotion, especially in aging populations:** Participants emphasized early detection, understanding, and treatment of neurodegenerative and psychiatric disorders, as well as brain health promotion, especially in aging populations. *Example quote: “How can we improve early detection of dementia disorders and Parkinson's disease, and further stimulate development of potential treatments?”*
3. **Impact of Societal and Environmental Stressors on the Brain:** Concerns were raised about how crises like climate change, war, and pandemics impact brain development and resilience across the lifespan. *Example quote: “The aftermath of climate changes, politics and war and how they altered coping mechanisms”*
4. **Neuroscience for Learning, Behavior Change, and Resilience:** Participants stressed the need for translational research that bridges abstract scientific insights with practical applications, public communication, and societal benefit. *Example quote: “How can we communicate and apply (abstract) findings in a useful way to other scientists and stakeholders.”*
5. **Individual Differences, Personalization, and Neuroscientific Integration:** There was strong interest in personalized approaches—studying individual variability through high-frequency longitudinal data, personalized medicine, and integrating cognitive, behavioral, and neural dimensions. *Example quote: “How do different brain, behavioural and environmental factors relate to each other. Can we differentiate between individual variations and shared processes, to develop targeted and personalised approaches?”*
6. **Cognitive and Neural Mechanisms in the Digital and Information Age:** Participants identified the need to study how digital environments—social media, misinformation, and technology use—affect cognition, brain development, and mental health, especially in vulnerable groups like youth. *Example quote: “Questions on e.g. fake news and*

disinformation from a fundamental neuroscience perspective. And questions on mental health.”

Appendix 2. Bibliometric analysis

Alphabetical list of keyphrases used in SciVal tool by Elsevier on July 15th, 2025. The labels used to name Topics are derived from the most frequent key phrases, as determined by semantic analysis of all paper titles, abstracts and keywords.

ADHD Across Lifespan and Functionality
ADHD and Its Connection to Obesity and Eating Disorders
ADHD and Its Connection to Substance Use Disorders
Adolescent Risk Behavior and Neural Development Insights
AMPA Receptor Dynamics in Synaptic Plasticity
Anhedonia and Neural Reward Processing in Depression
Aphasia Recovery through Brain Stimulation Techniques
Associative Learning Mechanisms in Classical Conditioning
Behavioral and Neurochemical Differences in Rat Strains
Behavioral Control and Decision-Making Mechanisms
Behavioral Insights into Obsessive Compulsive Disorder Models
Behavioral Management Strategies for Traumatic Brain Injury
Behavioral Systems and Personality Sensitivity Insights
Biological Correlates of Antisocial Behavior in Adolescents
Borderline Personality Disorder, Diagnostic and Therapies
Cell Adhesion Molecules in Cancer and Neurobiology
Cerebellar Contributions to Cognitive and Motor Functions
Cerebellar Development and Granule Cell Formation
Cerebellar Mechanisms in Motor Learning and Control
Cerebellar Mechanisms in Saccadic Eye Movements
Cerebral Amyloid Angiopathy and Microbleeds Impact
Chemogenetic Tools for Neural Circuit Manipulation
Childhood Trauma and Its Lasting Impact on Brain Development
Cholesterol Levels and Suicide Risk Correlation
Chronic Fatigue Syndrome and Quality of Life Insights
Circadian Rhythms and Mood Disorder Interactions
Circadian Rhythms and Social Influences on Behavior
Circadian Rhythms and Their Metabolic Implications
Cocaine Dependence and Neuroplasticity Mechanisms
Cognitive and Emotional Dimensions of Anorexia Nervosa
Cognitive Assessment Tools and Traditional Medicine Correlation
Cognitive Behavioral Therapy for Adult ADHD Treatment
Cognitive Behavioral Therapy for Insomnia Management
Cognitive Control and Hierarchical Representation in the Prefrontal Cortex
Cognitive Control Mechanisms in Error Processing
Cognitive Effects of Cannabis Use on Brain Function
Cognitive Enhancements through Video Game Engagement
Cognitive Impacts of Sleep Deprivation on Memory

Cognitive Impairment and Anesthesia in Surgery
Cognitive Impairment in Cocaine Dependence Treatment
Cognitive Impairment in Obstructive Sleep Apnea
Cognitive Load and Multimedia Learning Design
Cognitive Load Management in Learning Environments
Cognitive Networks in Attention and Executive Functions
Cognitive Penetration and Perceptual Experience Dynamics
Cognitive Performance and Behavioral Flexibility in Aves
Cognitive Performance Impacts of Sleep Deprivation
Cognitive Processes and Brain Connectivity Insights
Cognitive Processes in Eating Disorders and Bulimia
Cognitive Processes in Insight Problem Solving
Cognitive Reappraisal and Emotion Regulation Strategies
Cognitive Rehabilitation Strategies for Brain Injury Recovery
Cognitive Training Effects on Memory Function
Collective Behavior and Decision-Making in Animal Groups
Communication and Recovery in Locked-in Syndrome
Comorbidity of Eating Disorders and Substance Abuse
Computerized Cognitive Assessment and Ethical Governance
Connectivity and Function of the Bed Nucleus of the Stria Terminalis
Contextual Influences on Facial Emotion Perception
Cortical Interneuron Dynamics in Sensory Processing
Cortisol and Immune Response in PTSD
Cortisol and Memory: Stress Responses in the Brain
Cortisol Dynamics in Stress and Development
Cultural Competence and Trauma in Child Health Care
Decoding Neural Representations through fMRI Techniques
Delay Discounting and Impulsivity in Decision-Making
Dementia Care Models in Primary Health Systems
Dementia Risk Factors and Prevention Strategies
Depression and Cardiovascular Disease Interconnection
Dichotic Listening and Auditory Perception Asymmetry
Dietary Patterns and Their Impact on Depression
Digital Interventions for Mental Health Improvement
Digital Literacies and Online Information Comprehension
Disruptive Mood Disorders in Youth
Dopamine's Influence on Effort and Decision-Making
Dopamine's Role in Reward-Based Decision-Making
Dynamic Emotional Processes in Depression Assessment
Eating Disorders in Adolescents and Adults
EEG-fMRI Integration for Epilepsy Insights
Electrical Stimulation in Cognitive Rehabilitation Strategies
Electroencephalography Insights into Social Anxiety
Embodied Cognition and Semantic Representation Dynamics

Embodiment and Perception in Virtual Environments
Emotional Modulation of Startle Responses in Humans
Emotional Processing and Facial Expression Recognition
Emotional Processing and Visual Perception Mechanisms
Enhancing Vision Recovery in Hemianopia Patients
Estrogen Receptors and Cognitive Function in Women
Estrogen's Influence on Metabolic Health and Obesity
Evolutionary Insights into Brain Size and Function
Evolutionary Insights into Depression and Psychiatry
Exercise Addiction and Eating Disorder Interconnections
Eye Movement Desensitization for Trauma Recovery
Eyelid Reflex and Cognitive Dynamics in Patients
Face Recognition and Visual Perception
Facial Expression Dynamics and Emotional Responses
False Confessions and Interrogation Dynamics
False Memory Across Age Groups
Fear Conditioning and Anxiety Disorders
Food Addiction and Behavioral Patterns
Fragile X Syndrome: Insights into Neurodevelopmental Mechanisms
Functional Connectivity and Brain Mapping Insights
Functional Connectivity and Brain Structure in Insomnia
Functional Connectivity in Major Depressive Disorder
Functional Neurological and Conversion Disorders
Genetic Influences on Physical Activity Behavior
Genetic Influences on Serotonin Transporter Function
Genetic Insights into Mental Disorder Associations
Genetic Mechanisms and Pathways in Autism Spectrum Disorder
Genetic Variants and Neurodevelopmental Disorders in Autism
Heart Rate Variability Biofeedback in Stress Management
Hippocampal Mechanisms in Memory Representation
Hostility and Cardiovascular Disease Risk Factors
Hyperactivity and Anorexia Nervosa in Rodent Models
Illusory Contours and Visual Perception Dynamics
Imagery Rescripting in Mental Health Treatment
Impact of Social Isolation on Rat Behavior
Impulsivity and Cognitive Control in Behavioral Tasks
Impulsivity and Its Impact on Behavior
Individual Behavioral Variation in Animal Populations
Influences of Early Puberty on Adolescent Behavior
Innovative Therapies for Posttraumatic Stress Disorder
Interbrain Synchrony in Social Interactions
Interconnections Between Sleep Disorders and Chronic Pain
Interoceptive Awareness and Emotional Processing Insights
Interventions for Childhood Obesity Prevention in Europe

Ketamine's Antidepressant Effects and Mechanisms
Light's Influence on Circadian Rhythms and Health
Magnetoencephalography in Brain Activity Mapping
Mapping Cytoarchitecture of the Human Cerebral Cortex
Marmosets as Models for Human Health Research
Maternal Deprivation Effects on Stress Response
Melanin Concentrating Hormone in Energy Regulation
Memory Assessment Tools for Alzheimer's Disease
Memory Reconsolidation and Its Role in Fear Conditioning
Mental Health Challenges in Juvenile Justice Youth
Mental Health Impacts of COVID-19 Pandemic
Mental Representation and Text Comprehension Dynamics
Mental Stress and Its Impact on Coronary Health
Metacognitive Insights on Student Learning Performance
Microsaccades and Visual Perception Dynamics
Mindfulness Approaches in Substance Use Treatment
Mindfulness Meditation and Brain Connectivity Insights
Mismatch Negativity in Auditory Processing Mechanisms
Mobile Technology in Mental Health Interventions
Multisensory Integration and Auditory Perception Mechanisms
Neural Circuit Development in Retinal Pathways
Neural Dynamics of Social Decision-Making Processes
Neural Interfaces for Motor Control and Sensation
Neural Mechanisms in Anxiety Disorders and Treatments
Neural Mechanisms in Sentence Processing and Semantic Integration
Neural Mechanisms of Aggression and Impulsiveness
Neural Mechanisms of Consciousness and Perception
Neural Mechanisms of Decision-Making and Value Assessment
Neural Mechanisms of Emotion and Experience
Neural Mechanisms of Fear Conditioning and Memory
Neural Mechanisms of Self-Referential Processing
Neural Mechanisms of Taste and Texture Processing
Neural Mechanisms of Visual Attention and Perception
Neural Mechanisms of Visual Orientation and Processing
Neural Mechanisms of Working Memory in the Prefrontal Cortex
Neural Oscillations in Memory and Perception
Neural Responses to Infant Cuteness and Caregiving
Neurobiological Insights into Dyslexia and Reading Processes
Neurobiological Insights into Substance Use Disorders
Neurobiological Mechanisms of Drug Seeking Behavior
Neurobiological Mechanisms of Obesity and Eating Behavior
Neurobiological Mechanisms of Predator-Induced Fear Responses
Neurocognitive Insights into Posttraumatic Stress Disorder
Neurofeedback Applications in Brain Connectivity Enhancement

Neurogenesis and Its Role in Hippocampal Function
Neuroscience Insights in Teacher Education Practices
Neurovascular Coupling and Brain Mapping Techniques
NMDA Receptor Dynamics in Neurological Disorders
Olfactory and Trigeminal Responses in Human Perception
Optogenetics and Channelrhodopsin in Neural Control
Oxytocin and Vasopressin in Social Behavior Dynamics
Pediatric Traumatic Brain Injury Outcomes
Perceptual Distortions in Migraine and Art
Perceptual Learning Mechanisms in Visual and Tactile Domains
Physiological Regulation and Child Development Insights
Plasticity Mechanisms in Visual Cortex Development
Post-Stroke Fatigue and Quality of Life
Posttraumatic Stress Disorder Across Contexts
Predictive Processing and Active Inference in Neuroscience
Psychiatric Disorders Following Traumatic Brain Injury
Psychological Flexibility and Acceptance in Therapy
Psychometric Evaluation of Anxiety and Depression Measures
Psychopathy and Its Impact on Behavior
Rabies Virus Applications in Electrophysiology and Neuronal Mapping
Repetitive Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation in Depression Treatment
Resilience Factors in Adolescent Mental Health
Retrieval Practice and Metacognition in Learning
Reversible Lesions of the Corpus Callosum in Encephalopathy
Rhythm and Auditory Perception in Human Movement
Self-Awareness and Rehabilitation in Brain Injury
Self-Regulated Learning in Diverse Educational Environments
Sensory Processing Challenges in Autism Spectrum Disorder
Shame and Guilt in Adolescents
Sleep Disorders and Alzheimer's Disease Connection
Sleep Disorders and Their Impact on Suicidal Ideation
Sleep Disorders in Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder
Sleep's Role in Memory Consolidation and Brain Activity
Social Dynamics and Emotional Responses in Rodents
Social Isolation and Loneliness in Older Adults
Social Withdrawal and Inhibition in Youth
Somatoform Disorders and Health Anxiety
Spatial Memory and Navigation in Diverse Species
Spatial Memory Mechanisms in Rodent Navigation
Split-Brain Dynamics and Consciousness
Steady-State Visual Evoked Potentials in Brain-Computer Interfaces
Subject-Verb Agreement in Language Production
Support Systems for Caregivers of Dementia Patients
Synaptic Mechanisms in Neurotransmission and Endocytosis

Takotsubo Cardiomyopathy and Its Triggers
Testosterone and Its Influence on Human Behavior
Theory of Mind and Social Cognition Insights
Tonic Immobility and Posttraumatic Stress Responses
Transcranial Alternating Current Stimulation Effects on Brain Activity
Transcranial Direct Current Stimulation in Cognitive Enhancement
Transient Global Amnesia and Memory Function Insights
Traumatic Brain Injury and Community Integration Outcomes
Traumatic Brain Injury and Youth Offending Dynamics
Understanding Aggression through Social Information Processing
Vagus Nerve Stimulation in Neuromodulation Therapy
VGF Peptides in Energy Regulation and Disease
Vigilance Performance and Sustained Attention Dynamics
Virtual Reality Applications in Anxiety Treatment
Visceral Insights into Sleep and Brain Function
Visual Memory Capacity and Attention Dynamics
Visual Perception and Motor Control in Grasping
Visual Perception and Scene Recognition Mechanisms
Visual Search Dynamics and Attention Mechanisms
Vocal Communication and Acoustic Variation in Birds
Vocal Learning Mechanisms in Songbirds and Humans
Wearable Sensors Transforming Sleep Monitoring
Working Memory Development Across Cognitive Domains